

ACTIVE METHODS OF DEVELOPING CONVERSATIONAL SPEECH WHEN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the meaning and features of the use of active methods in the process of teaching foreign languages. Some effective ways of conducting classes are presented that can be used to effectively develop speaking skills when teaching a foreign language.*

Keywords: *active methods, creative approach, independent work, oral speech, case method, project activity.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'qitish jarayonida faol usullardan foydalanishning ahamiyati va xususiyatlari muhokama qilinadi. Chet tilini o'qitishda og'zaki nutq ko'nikmalarini samarali rivojlantirish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin bo'lgan darslarni o'tkazishning ba'zi samarali usullari taqdim etiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *faol usullar, ijodiy yondashuv, mustaqil ish, og'zaki nutq, keys usuli, loyiha faoliyati.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются значение и особенности применения активных методов в процессе обучения иностранных языков. Представляются некоторые результативные способы проведения занятий, которые можно использовать для эффективного развития навыков устной речи при обучении иностранного языка.*

Ключевые слова: *активные методы, творческий подход, самостоятельная работа, устная речь, кейс-метод, проектная деятельность.*

Currently, with the development of the information society and globalization in the higher education system of our country, as well as throughout the world, there is a need for teachers to develop new knowledge in information literacy, which contributes to the emergence of a new type of education, innovative, in which information technology should play the role of system integration. Orientation towards new educational goals and competencies requires not only changing the content of academic subjects, but also methods and forms of organizing the educational process, increasing student activity in the classroom, and bringing together teaching topics.

As is known, traditional education methods are aimed at giving students as much knowledge as possible. Teachers convey information that they themselves already possess and decide what skills need to be developed from their own point of view. The students' task is to reproduce as completely and accurately as possible the knowledge created by others. The knowledge gained through such training is encyclopedic in nature and represents a certain amount of information on various academic topics. There is a shift from knowledge acquisition to skill building, and the orientation of learning is being restructured towards a character-oriented approach. “My students will not learn new things from me; they will discover this new thing themselves. My main task is to help them open up and develop their own ideas,” wrote I.G. Pestalozzi.

In the context of developmental pedagogy, it is necessary to ensure maximum activity of the students themselves in the development of key abilities, since this type of abilities are formed only through the experience of their own activities. Therefore, many researchers associate innovations in education with interactive teaching methods, which include all types of activities

that require a creative approach to the material and provide conditions for the disclosure of information for each student [2, 3]. The most modern forms of the active method, which include interactive methods, include various types of lectures, discussions, heuristic conversations, brainstorming, role-playing and simulation games, case methods, project methods, group work with visual materials, discussion of videos, video discussions and others.

When teaching a foreign language, a teacher can achieve the creation of an effective speech environment only during the communicative activities of students in small or large groups in the classroom. The ability to communicate clearly and effectively in a foreign language helps students develop their language skills and succeed in their future careers. For this reason, during the lesson, foreign language teachers should pay more attention to the development of students' oral speech, providing a rich environment for establishing communicative communication [3], rather than memorization. In this regard, this article presents some effective methods that can be used to develop oral communication skills in a foreign language, in particular English.

One of the effective methods of teaching foreign languages is the project method [4]. Project activities of students using the latest educational technologies contribute to the formation of key competencies. The project method develops students' cognitive abilities, creative spontaneity, the ability to think independently, the ability to find and solve problems, the ability to navigate the information space, the ability to predict and evaluate the results of their own activities. The project method is always focused on independent work, which students do individually, in pairs or groups over a certain period of time. This method can be used when there is a truly significant problem (practical, scientific, creative and others). At the same time, the teacher advises and guides students on all issues that arise and helps them understand the educational material.

Project-based Teaching Strategy

Another productive method of teaching foreign languages is the case method. The essence of this method is that the student needs to understand the real situation, the explanation of which not only reflects the practical problem, but also what needs to be learned when solving this problem. At the same time, there are no clear solutions to the problem itself. While working on a case, students research and analyze additional information from various areas of knowledge, and also consider a future career. As practice has shown, this is an interactive teaching method that creates a positive attitude among students, who consider it a game for mastering theoretical concepts and mastering the practical application of the material. When working on cases, students develop the following components of key competencies: the ability to solve problems,

communication skills, the ability to reflect, the ability to apply professional knowledge in practice, the ability to negotiate, the ability to take responsibility.

Stages of the case method

Case methods in combination with other technologies can be thought of as complex systems into which other, less complex recognition methods are integrated. These include modeling, systems analysis, problem-based methods, thought experiments, descriptive methods, classification, discussion, game methods and other methods. When using this method as an assignment, you may require students (or groups of students) to write a report or prepare a project or computer presentation.

Currently, one of the most common technologies for teaching a foreign language is working in small groups. This technology gives everyone the opportunity to participate and practice collaboration and interpersonal skills, especially the ability to actively listen, form common ground, and resolve disagreements. All this is often impossible to do in large groups. This method is effectively used to develop such practical skills as writing advertisements, writing resumes [5], as well as when preparing arguments on proposed topics (for example, “What should a modern journalist be like?”).

The case study method involves presenting students with a specific situation. Students are tasked with making collaborative management decisions in specific situations. To improve the level of education, groups can be organized, each of which will provide its own version of the solution (in the form of a review or public defense). This method is recommended to be used when it comes to an independent and relatively complex task, and only the correct solution of which is known to the teacher in advance. He has the last word when summing up the results.

Thus, the development of speaking skills when teaching a foreign language is one of the most important factors in the educational process. The ability to communicate clearly and effectively in a second language leads to a student's success in their future professional endeavors. Therefore, instead of focusing students on mere memorization, language teachers should pay serious attention to oral language development and focus on creating a rich learning environment in which meaningful communication occurs. To this end, various speaking activities like those listed above can go a long way in helping students develop the basic communication skills needed for speaking.

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